

Research programme to share knowledge and improve uptake of new digital technologies in sheep and goat farming

Strong network all around Europe

Training days
12

Innovative farms

Digifarms

18 Demo days

1350+
Stakeholders
involved

- 1** Final Seminar in Scotland
- 1** International visit in New Zealand
- 52** National Workshops
- 5** Transnational Workshops

Sm@RT outputs

Extensive dissemination of results

Head of consortium:

Partners:

Agencia pro sa chrcina in agricoltura
Agencia regionale per la ricerca in agricoltura

AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITY

www.emu.ee
Estonian University of Life Sciences

Innovation Croissance

INSTITUT DE L'ÉLEVAGE IDELE

NIBIO

National partner:

UNIVERSITY OF DEBRECEN

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